

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Physiology and plant nutrition

***Sesbania rostrata* and *Aeschynomene afraaspera* effects on crop establishment of transplanted lowland rice**

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Anaerobic decomposition products in flooded soils may affect root and shoot growth of newly transplanted rice seedlings after organic matter amendment. We evaluated the effects of *S. rostrata* and *A. afraaspera* green manure (GM) amendment on crop establishment of transplanted lowland rice by conducting a field experiment at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center (MRRTC), Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, during the 1988 dry season.

The soil is a Vertic Tropaquept with pH 5.9. Each kilogram of soil contains 14 g organic C, 1.1 g total N, CEC 38 cmol_c, 450 g clay, and 50 g sand. The field was irrigated and kept flooded for 2 wk before wetland preparation to allow the soil redox potential to reach equilibrium. The field was plowed once (15- to 20-cm depth) and harrowed twice. We broadcast and incorporated single superphosphate, KCl, and zinc sulfate heptahydrate at 26-50-4.5 kg P-K-Zn/ha before transplanting rice.

GM plants grown for 45 d outside the trial area were harvested, transferred to the experimental field, chopped into 5-cm-long pieces, and incorporated by hand into moist soil after the flooded plots were drained 1 d before transplanting. GM was basally incorporated at 90 kg N/ha using 2.9 t dry matter/ha for *S. rostrata* (3.2% N, C/N = 12) and 2.43 t/ha for *A. afraaspera* (3.7% N, C/N = 12). We compared these GM treatments with urea N application at the same rate and with a zero fertilizer N control.

The experimental design was a randomized complete block with four replications.

Crop growth rates and N uptake rates of transplanted IR64 rice as affected by *Sesbania rostrata* and *Aeschynomene afraaspera* GM or urea application. MRRTC. Muñoz. Nueva Ecija, Philippines. 1988 dry season.

N source ^a	Crop growth rates (g/m ² per d)		N uptake rates (mg/m ² per d)	
	5-13 DT	13-20 DT	5-13 DT	13-20 DT
<i>S. rostrata</i>	0.8	2.3	25	112
<i>A. afraaspera</i>	0.7	2.1	24	110
Urea	1.4	7.0	51	245
No fertilizer N	1.9	3.9	61	145
LSD (0.05)	0.3	1.2	9	21

^a N rate: 90 kg/ha as GM basally applied, or as urea applied in 2/3-1/3 split.

Twenty-one-day-old IR64 rice seedlings were transplanted into water-saturated soil at 3-4 plants/hill at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Plots were 29.4 m². Floodwater depth was kept at 5 cm after transplanting.

Six rice hills were sampled at 5 d after transplanting (DT) and weekly thereafter until panicle initiation (PI) to determine dry weight, N content, and N uptake. After PI, four hills were sampled biweekly until crop maturity.

Yellowing of plants and rice seedling death were observed in the first 7 DT. Missing hills were replaced. Plant damage may have been due partly to transplanting shock, but symptoms were more severe in GM treatments.

Crop growth rates and N uptake rates were significantly lower ($P = 0.05$) in GM treatments than in urea and control treatments (see table). *A. afraaspera* seemed to damage rice seedlings more than *S. rostrata* did, but this was not significantly reflected in their crop growth rates.

Exchangeable NH₄⁺-N levels at the

MRRTC site were high enough (data not presented) to provide N for the rice seedlings as proven by the higher crop growth rate with zero fertilizer N than with GM. Therefore, other factors must have affected seedling vigor.

High concentrations of soil CO₂ due to GM decomposition and the release of organic acids, phenolic substances, and other organic compounds probably affected seedling root and shoot growth. However, rice plants overcame the additional stress caused by GM amendment and gave the same N uptake at 34 DT and dry matter at 41 DT as did plants fertilized with urea (data not presented).

In this experiment where missing rice hills were replaced, grain yields in urea and GM treatments did not significantly differ (data not presented). But in farmers' fields, where dead rice hills are not replanted, farmers should delay transplanting by a few days after GM incorporation to avoid problems in establishing the crop. □

Response to different Zn carriers of rice grown on Ustifluvents in India

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We studied the relative efficiency of Zn carriers applied as foliar sprays for rice on Ustifluvents. Soil was sandy loam with pH 8.4, EC 0.30 dS/m, 0.45% organic C, and 0.45 mg DTPA extractable Zn/kg soil.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Urea, diammonium phosphate, and muriate of potash were applied at 120 kg N, 27 kg P, and 24 kg K/ha.

We transplanted 45-d-old seedlings of long-duration, short-statured rice variety Jaya and applied three types of Zn in foliar sprays at two concentrations each (see table). Plants were sprayed 4 wk after transplanting and twice more at a 10-d interval. The crop was grown to maturity and the yield

Effect of foliar sprays of Zn on the yield and zinc uptake by rice.

Zn source	Concentration of Zn solution (%)	Yield (t/ha)		Zn uptake (g/ha)
		Grain	Straw	
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.10	5.3	9.2	301
	0.20	5.8	10.8	394
Zn-EDTA	0.01	5.4	9.4	231
	0.10	6.0	11.5	350
Zn-chelate (with phenolic group)	0.02	5.0	9.4	202
	0.10	5.6	10.2	310
Control		4.3	7.4	135
LSD (P = 0.05)		0.6	1.2	58

recorded. Grain and straw samples were collected, processed, and analyzed for Zn content.

Rice grain yield significantly increased with foliar sprays of Zn, regardless of Zn source (see table). Higher Zn concentrations increased grain yield, but the effect was significant only for the chelated form.

Zn-EDTA at 0.1% produced the highest yield of 6 t grain/ha, which was

significantly superior to that with ZnSO₄·7H₂O but at par with Zn-chelate. A similar pattern of yield response was observed for rice straw. Zn uptake in rice increased significantly the rates of all the tested sources.

This study suggests that Zn applied as Zn-EDTA is more efficient at correcting Zn deficiency in rice than either ZnSO₄ or Zn-chelate. □

Fertilizer management—inorganic

Long-term effect of inorganic fertilizers, lime, and straw on lowland rice in Kerala

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We are conducting a study of the long-term effects of continuous application of N, P, K, lime, and straw incorporation on lowland rice. This interim report covers the first consecutive 4 yr from rabi (wet season) 1987-88 to rabi 1990-91.

The field experiment has a permanent layout of 40-m² plots in randomized block design with three replications and nine treatments. The soil is a hydromorphic silty clay with initial pH 4.8, EC 0.1 dS/m, 3.4% organic carbon (OC), 7 kg available P/ha, and 100 kg available K/ha. Treatments consist of combinations of 90-20-38 kg NPK/ha and lime, a control, straw incorporation, and soil test recommendation (STR). STRs were 49-23-40-900 kg NPK and lime/ha for the first 2 yr, 82-14-35-1450 for the third yr, and 49-16-40-700 for the fourth yr.

Rice crop was harvested at about 10 cm above ground level. For the straw incorporation treatment, straw was returned to the respective plots after recording yield.

Lime was applied at first plowing, when the straw was also incorporated.

Rice variety Pavizham (MO-6, 120 d) was wet seeded at 100 kg/ha until 1989 kharif (monsoon); thereafter transplanting at 15- × 15-cm spacing was used. Fertilizers were applied as urea, mussoorie rock phosphate, and muriate of potash as per treatment; N and K in two equal splits as

basal and at panicle initiation stage; and P as fully basal. Weeds were controlled by herbi-cides and/or hand weeding.

Pooled analyses of the data revealed that the treatments, seasons, years, and treatments × seasons interactions were statistically significant in grain yield. Variations in grain yield was not significant during kharif (see table). During rabi, all the treatments that provided 90 kg N/ha and STR were statistically on par and produced significantly higher grain yields than the treatments that received no N.

No interactions were statistically significant for straw yield despite significant treatment and seasonal and annual

variations. Straw yield and growth and yield attributes, such as plant height, panicles/m² and panicle weight, varied significantly with treatment and followed grain yield trends, but had no significant interactions.

Soil analyses data showed that treatments produced no significant variation in pH, EC, OC, and available P and K in the soil.

Results show that in the lowlands of Kerala, rice responds to applied fertilizers only during rabi. Among the three major nutrients, only N produced a significant response. Straw incorporation and lime application had no measurable effect on yield. STR overpredicts the need for lime and hence appears uneconomic. □

Effect of inorganic fertilizers, lime, and straw on rice. Kerala, India, 1987-91.

Treatment (kg NPK/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle weight (g)	Available P in the soil (kg/ha)
	Kharif	Rabi	Mean					
Control	2.0	2.4	2.3	2.5	71.8	269	1.96	12.4
Straw alone	2.0	2.5	2.3	2.4	72.2	295	1.89	15.2
90-0-0	2.2	3.0	2.6	3.1	78.3	315	2.32	9.6
90-20-0	2.2	3.4	2.8	3.3	77.3	309	2.24	8.8
90-0-38	2.4	3.1	2.7	3.2	78.0	303	2.27	9.2
0-20-38	2.0	2.4	2.2	2.4	73.5	270	2.18	8.8
90-20-38	2.2	2.7	2.5	3.4	76.7	316	2.35	10.8
90-20-38 + 600 kg lime/ha	1.9	3.1	2.5	3.1	78.9	313	2.27	9.2
Soil test recommendation	2.1	3.1	2.6	3.4	77.3	317	2.37	8.0
LSD ^a (0.05)		0.6	0.5	0.5	4.6	35	0.28	ns

^a LSD to compare treatments × seasons interaction means.

Large granule urea (LGU), an efficient and economic source of N for wetland rice

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The N-use efficiency of prilled urea (PU) in wetland rice is 20-50%. Rock phosphate-coated urea (RPCU), gypsum-coated urea (GCU), and sulfur-coated urea (SCU) are costly to produce; urea supergranules (USG) are expensive to apply. These costs reduce their economic benefit although they supply N more efficiently than PU. LGU is a new